

Synthesis of cross-linked graft copolymer hydrogel from maleic acid, poly(vinyl alcohol) and methylene bisacrylamide, and studies on its efficiency in uptaking zinc ion from aqueous solution

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Abstract : A novel graft copolymer hydrogel from maleic acid and poly(vinyl alcohol) has been synthesized and it is cross-linked by methylene bisacrylamide for the investigation of its efficiency in uptaking zinc ion from aqueous solution. The swelling behavior, temperature sensitivity, gel content and swelling rate of the hydrogel were investigated. Metal ion uptake capacity of the polymer was evaluated in the light of changing pH, temperature, time and concentration. The polymer was characterized by chemical, thermal (TGA) and spectral (FTIR) data analysis. Surface morphology was inspected with the help of SEM photograph. A plausible mechanism for zinc ion exchange has been suggested. The selectivity of the polymer towards metal ion has been investigated. Zinc ion has been isolated quantitatively from various synthetic mixture containing metal ions (Ni^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+}), commonly found in the effluent of galvanization industry.

Keywords : Graft co-polymerization, cross-linking, hydrogel, zinc ion, ion-exchange.

Introduction

Zinc, cadmium and mercury are the prior toxic metals. Zinc is the most important because of its wide application as alloys and brass, galvanizing steel¹ and iron products, rubber and paints, mining and electroplating, etc. Due to abundant use of zinc and its toxicity, it is necessary to develop reliable, efficient and cost effective methods for control or removal of zinc from industrial and municipal waste prior to release into natural water systems.

There are many removal methods available for zinc such as solvent extraction², ion-exchange³, adsorption⁴, etc. Metal ion adsorption onto solid polymer surface (Solid phase extraction, SPE) is now considered one of the most promising techniques for concentration^{5,6}, removal and recovery of metal ions from wide variety of sources⁶ due to its cost effectiveness, eco-friendliness and rapidness. Immobilizing functional group, pH of the medium, presence of masking agents, temperature, etc., can control the selectivity of these materials towards metal ion. The polymeric matrix affects other properties, namely the ion-exchange capacity, kinetic features, mechanical and chemi-

cal strength, and regeneration⁷.

In the present decade, several researchers⁸⁻¹³ are engaged in synthesizing suitable hydrogels having selective metal ion binding capacity. Very few of them⁹⁻¹³ are reported to be useful for removal and recovery of zinc ion from aqueous solutions. The use of PVA based hydrogels as biomaterials has recently gained great importance in view of the low toxicity, non-carcinogenic and high biocompatibility. Therefore a number of methods have been reported for preparation of PVA hydrogels. One of the useful ways to make PVA hydrogels is low temperature gelatin of PVA in aqueous solutions. However, there are no reports on the grafting of maleic acid (MA) onto PVA and subsequent cross-linking by methylene bisacrylamide. Cross-linked MA-g-PVA is expected to have better metal ion-binding capacity with faster kinetics than that of uncross-linked one. PVA is a cheaper and its sorption properties can be enhanced by the graft copolymerization¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

In the present work, a new procedure for concentrating zinc(II) ion by MA-g-PVA (cross-linked by methylene bisacrylamide) has been developed.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

Poly(vinyl alcohol) (Burgoyne Burbidges, viscosity average molecular weight = 16100, degree of hydrolysis = 98.5–99.0 mol %, viscosity = 30 cps) was used. Maleic acid (Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mol. wt. = 133) was purified by distillation and the middle fraction was used. Ceric ammonium sulphate (Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.), methylene bisacrylamide (Fluka, Buchs, Switzerland), zinc nitrate (Merck, Mumbai, India) and sulfuric acid (Merck, Mumbai, India, 98%, Sp. gr. = 1.84, Mol. wt. = 98.08) were used as received.

Equipments :

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the polymer were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR (Model No. 8400s) using KBr pellets. Thermal analysis was conducted using a Stanton Red Craft Thermal Analyzer (STA-780) in air at a rate of 10 °C/min. The amount of metal ion in the solution was measured using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS, Shimadzu, AA 6300) and complexometrically. An Elico LI-120 pH meter, thermostat and chromatographic column (i.d. = 0.8 cm) were used. Scanning electron micrograph (SEM) was taken by a camera (S-570, Japan).

Synthesis of cross-linked graft copolymer :

Cross-linking of PVA was carried out in a two-necked round-bottomed flask at 70 °C. A definite amount of PVA (0.5 g) was mixed with water (20 ml) and maleic acid (0.3 g) is added and heated for 15 min, then concentrated sulphuric acid (2 ml) and CAS (0.2 g) added and stirred. Nitrogen atmosphere was maintained throughout the reaction period. After an hour methylene bisacrylamide (0.1 g) was mixed to cross-link the grafted product. Quenching with hydroquinone arrested cross-linking reaction after 1 h. The precipitated cross-linked polymer was separated by filtration and washed several time with 1 : 10 H₂SO₄ (v/v). The un-reacted PVA were separated by prolonged (24 h) extraction with water in a Soxhlet apparatus. Finally, the sample was extracted with acetone for 72 h to dissolve all other impurities. The colorless product was dried under vacuum at 100 °C for 72 h to a constant weight. The dried solid was grounded and screened through a set of sieves for the particles of the size ranged between 0.16 to 0.27 mm for conducting experiments.

Determination of degree of swelling, swelling rate and gel fraction :

The samples were immersed in purified water and weighted in definite time interval for 72 h and swelling was calculated by using eq. (1)¹⁸ :

$$\text{Degree of swelling (\%)} = (W_s - W_d)/W_d \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_s and W_d are the weight of the swollen polymer and the weight of dried hydrogel respectively.

The swelling rate (SR, g/g.min) was defined as follows¹⁸,

$$\text{SR} = S_t/t_{mr} \quad (2)$$

In which S_t stands for swelling at the time related to minimum rate parameter, t_{mr} (min), obtained for the hydrogels from a set of experiments.

Gel fraction of the prepared polymer was determined by immersing the sample in water and heated it at 100 °C with constant stirring for 8 h. The sample was then dried in 100 °C. Gel fraction then calculated by using the following equation¹⁸,

$$G = W_g/W_o \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where G , W_g and W_o are the gel fraction (%) and the weight of sample after and before extractions respectively.

Retention and recovery procedure :

Retention by batch method was carried out with suitable mechanical agitation (90–100 rpm) and temperature (5 to 40 °C). To determine the retention of zinc ion, 0.05 g of prepared polymer (X-MA-g-PVA) was taken into a 100 ml beaker with 10 ml metal solution. The concentration of zinc(II) ion in aqueous solution was kept within 65 to 650 mg/L (ppm). The pH of the solution was maintained at 5.5. One ml solution of the sample was withdrawn each time from the reaction mixture by a syringe at a gap of fixed time interval and analyzed for kinetic study. The selectivity of the prepared resin among various metal ions (Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II}, commonly found in galvanizing waste) was determined by a competitive batch method. Resin sample (0.05 g) was equilibrated for 60 min with 10 ml solution (3.3 ml of each metal ion solution, which contained 0.001 mole metal ion). The adsorbed metal ions were sequentially eluted (desorbed) with the selective stripping agents.

Treatment of data :

All the experiments were performed at least in triplicate at room temperature (27 °C). The retention capacity

(Q , mg/g), percentage of recovery (R), degree of grafting (G) and cross-link density (q) was calculated from the following relations¹⁹,

$$Q = \text{Metal retention (mg)/polymer added (g)} \quad (4)$$

$$R = \text{Metal ion eluted (g)} \times 100/\text{Metal ion originally bound to polymer (g)} \quad (5)$$

$$G = \text{Polymer grafted (g)/PVA added (g)} \quad (6)$$

$$q = M_0/M_c \quad (7)$$

where M_0 = molecular weight of the repeating unit, M_c = average molecular mass between consecutive cross-link¹⁹.

Results and discussion

Evidence for the formation of cross-linked graft copolymer :

FTIR spectra of the cross-linked graft copolymer of

PVA (X-MA-g-PVA) are shown in Table 1. The spectrum of the grafted polymer exhibits all the characteristics peaks of PVA. In addition, two new peaks at 1723 and 1650 cm^{-1} are observed. The bands at 1723 and 1650 cm^{-1} are due to carbonyl stretching frequency of carboxylic acid and secondary amide respectively²⁰, which suggest the grafting of poly(maleic acid) onto PVA and cross-linking by bisacrylamide. Polymers exhibit a peak at 3435 cm^{-1} and 3360 cm^{-1} that corresponds to both polymeric -OH and -NH bonds²⁰. Since the cross-linked graft copolymer of PVA contains both -OH and -NH groups, the peak intensity is higher than that of PVA.

Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) traces of (X-MA-g-PVA) are shown in Fig. 1. This figure indicates that there are four steps weight loss. First step (35–95 °C \approx 16%), second step weight loss (95–160 °C \approx 17%), third step weight

Table 1. Assignment of IR peaks

Peak position (cm^{-1})	Nature of peak (intensity)	Peak assignment
1200–1235	Broad, medium intensity	C–C long skeleton, C–O stretching
1650	Sharp, strong intensity	Carbonyl stretching of a secondary amide
1723	Sharp, strong intensity	Carbonyl stretching of carboxylic acid
2875	Sharp, strong intensity	C–H stretching of an alkane
2924	Broad, strong intensity	-CH ₂ stretching of poly(vinyl alcohol)
3360	Broad, medium intensity	N–H stretching of an amide
3435	Broad, strong intensity	O–H stretching of alcohol

Fig. 1. TGA and DTA traces of grafted PVA (X-MA-g-PVA).

loss (160–270 °C \approx 31%) and fourth step (>270 °C > 34%) of the polymer due to removal of water, carbon dioxide, nitrogen and impurities. Thus the change in weight loss pattern from three steps for PVA to four steps for modified PVA clearly indicates the simultaneous grafting by MA and cross-linking by MBA. The endothermic peak at 100 °C of the polymers justifies the evolution of water during heating.

IPDT (integral procedure decomposition temperature)²¹ was calculated from TGA curves

$$\text{IPDT (}^\circ\text{C)} = A.K.(T_f - T_i) + T_i$$

where $A = (S_1 + S_2)/S_1 + S_2 + S_3$ and $K = (S_1 + S_2)/S_1$; T_i = initial temperature 35 °C, T_f = final temperature 460 °C, S_1 , S_2 and S_3 indicate the specified area in TGA curve.

The value of IPDT of PVA is 350 °C and for the prepared polymer it is 672 °C. Higher IPDT value indicates the better thermal stability of the grafted polymer.

IDT (initial decomposition temperature)²² and FDT (final decomposition temperature)²² are found to be 35 and 270 °C respectively. The endothermic peak around 325 °C may be due to melting of the polymer.

Physical and chemical characteristics :

The physicochemical characteristics of the synthesized polymer (X-MA-g-PVA) are given here. The surface area of cross-linked polymer was determined by methylene blue adsorption method¹⁹ and was found to be 76.64 m²/g. The exchange capacity of the exchanger (4.8 meq H⁺/g) was superior to the literature value of commercially available many cation exchangers²² such as SRS-100 (1.85), Versatic-10 (2.11), and uncross-linked MA-g-PVA (3.4). Higher specific surface area and greater pore size are the probable reasons for superior exchange capacity of cross-linked polymer compared to uncross-linked one. Average molecular weight between two consecutive cross-link, cross-link density, degree of grafting, gel fraction, swelling rate and pore size of the material were 604 g/mol, 0.127, 9, 56%, 6.4 and 37.34 Å respectively. Fig. 2 shows the SEM photograph of X-MA-g-PVA. It is clear from SEM image (Fig. 2) that the surface of the polymer is heterogeneous with separated domains.

Effect of time and temperature on the equilibrium degree of swelling :

Fig. 3 shows that swelling behaviors of grafted cross-

Fig. 2. SEM photograph of the grafted PVA (X-MA-g-PVA).

Fig. 3. Effect of time and temperature on the degree of swelling of grafted PVA hydrogels (1, 2, 3 and 4 represent 27, 40, 45, 50 °C respectively).

linked PVA which was measured in different temperature of double distilled water. It was found that 75% of swelling completed within 20 h and it will be equilibrium at 50 h. Swelling of hydrogels was found to decrease with increases in temperature. All PVA hydrogels showed temperature responsive swelling behavior base on the association/dissociation of hydrogen bonding¹⁸.

Influence of pH on zinc ion retention and retention mechanism :

The results on Zn^{II} retention at various pH (2.5–6) are shown in Fig. 4. The retention capacity of the polymer was increased with pH from 2.5 to 5.5 and then levels off with the further increase of pH^{23,24}. The optimum pH was found to be 5.5.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on zinc ion retention (Sorbent dose = 1.5 g/L, Sorbate dose = 65 ppm, Time = 1 h, Temperature = 27 °C).

The zinc ion goes to the exchange site mainly through ion exchange process (eq. 8). The presence of exchangeable H⁺ (exchange capacity = 4.8 meq H⁺/g) favors the ion exchange process. The absence of sharp peak at 1723 cm⁻¹ and appearance of a new peak at 1595 cm⁻¹ in the FTIR spectrum of zinc uptaking exchanger clearly indicates the presence of carboxylate anion¹⁹ in the metal loaded sample.

At low pH (<5.5) the equilibrium shifts towards left. As a result, less amount of Zn^{II} was uptake at pH 2.5. While at relatively higher pH (>5.5), the zinc ion undergoes hydrolysis and interfere the exchange process²⁵. As a result retention capacity levels off at pH beyond 5.5.

Effect of sorbate dose on metal ion retention :

The effect of sorbate dose (Zn^{II} concentration) on retention, keeping the other conditions (pH = 5.5, temperature = 27 °C, sorbent dose = 1.5 g/L and time = 1 h) fixed, was studied. It was observed that zinc ion uptake capacity of the sorbent increases sharply with the

increase of metal ion concentration. The zinc ion retention capacity of the resin (X-MA-g-PVA) was 38.45 mg/g at low level of sorbate (65 ppm) and became 78 mg/g at 650 ppm of zinc. The maximum uptake capacity was found to be 234.6 mg/g at relatively higher dose of sorbate (2600 ppm).

Retention of Zn^{II} in the competitive condition :

In this group of experiments, the competitive retention of nickel, cadmium and zinc ions into the polymer were investigated. These experiments were performed at a constant pH (5.5), temperature (27 °C), sorbent dose (1.5 g/L) and time (1 h) with the solution containing 0.001 mole of each metal ion. The retention capacities were 0.590, 0.081 and 0.063 mmol/g for zinc, nickel and cadmium ions respectively (Table 2). The order of affinity under competitive condition was the same as that obtained for single ion solutions [i.e. Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Cd^{II}]. The stability constants (*K*_{stability}) for the various metal/resin complexes were investigated with Ruzic²⁶ method. The *K*_{stability} values for the complexes were 685, 512 and 204 L/mol for Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} respectively. The maximum amount of the zinc ion uptake was consistent with the higher stability constant values obtained.

The selective retention of the resin for Zn^{II}-Ni^{II}-Cd^{II} mixture solution is shown in Table 3. By comparing the results of selectivity coefficient²⁷ (*K*) of the resin for Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cd^{II}, it is also suggested that the selective separation of Zn^{II} is prior to Ni^{II} and Cd^{II}.

Effect of contact time and temperature :

Fig. 5 shows the amount of Zn^{II} uptaking (*Q*₁, mg/g) at a contact time, *t* (min). The results have indicated that ~87% adsorption took place in 35 min, and the time required to reach the equilibrium is 60 min that is much less than reported values of commercially available car-

Table 2. Competitive retention and elution of Ni^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} ions

Metal ions	Metal ions retention (mg/g of polymer)	Metal ions retention (mmol/g of polymer)	Eluent used	Volume of eluent (ml)	Recovery (%)
Ni ^{II}	4.60	0.081	0.002 M H ₂ SO ₄	20	83.30
Cd ^{II}	7.25	0.063	0.01 M HNO ₃	20	74.07
Zn ^{II}	38.07	0.590	0.05 M H ₂ SO ₄	40	94.07

Table 3. Selectivity retention of the resin for Ni^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} ions

Resin	Retention capacity (mmol/g)			Selectivity coefficient (K)	
	Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	$K_{Zn^{2+}/Ni^{2+}}$	$K_{Zn^{2+}/Cd^{2+}}$
	X-MA-g-PVA	1.98	0.24	0.15	8.25

Conditions : The initial concentration of metal ion was 650 ppm, the pH value of 5.5, shaking 24 h at 27 °C.

boxylic resins²². The rapid retention in the initial part may be attributed to the availability of the negatively charged surface of the sorbent (RCOO⁻). The slow retention in the later part may be due to electrostatic hindrance between adsorbed positively charged sorbate and available cationic sorbate in solution, and the slow pore diffusion of the solution into the bulk of polymer. The similar types of results were observed by previous work²⁰.

The effect of temperature on Zn^{II} retention at various time is shown in Fig. 5. The retention capacity increases with the increasing temperature from 5 to 40 °C. The retention and recovery occurred through ion exchange process (eq. 8). Initial increase of temperature favors the retention^{20,28}, while increase of temperature above 40°C accelerates the elution process.

Fig. 5. Effect of time on Zn²⁺ retention (Sorbent dose = 1.5 g/L, Sorbate dose = 65, pH = 5.5).

Method of Zn²⁺ separation and its analytical application :

It was possible to separate Zn²⁺ from several metal ions present in binary mixture by using selective stripping agents. Each binary mixture was prepared by mixing an aliquot of standard solution of Zn²⁺ (2.65 mg/L) and one of the diverse metal ions at desired pH (A to C, Table 4). At pH 5.5, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ were co-extracted quantitatively along with Zn²⁺ from their respective binary mixtures. Zn²⁺ was eluted first from

Table 4. Separation of Zn²⁺ from synthetic metal ion mixtures

Mixture	Cations	Added (mg)	Recovered		RSD (%)	RSD (%)	Eluent (M) (mL)
			(mg)	(mg)			
A	Zn ²⁺	2.65	2.62	2.64	3.62	3.32	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ (70)
	Cd ²⁺	1.80	1.68	1.72	3.20	3.16	0.010 HNO ₃ (55)
B	Zn ²⁺	2.65	2.62	2.64	1.94	1.74	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ (70)
	Ni ²⁺	2.15	2.10	2.12	1.52	1.31	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ (50)
C	Zn ²⁺	2.65	2.65	2.66	1.94	1.81	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ (70)
	Cu ²⁺	2.85	2.50	2.52	2.18	2.13	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ (45)
D	Ni ²⁺	2.15	2.15	2.18	2.05	1.78	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ (60)
	Cd ²⁺	1.80	1.68	1.67	2.71	2.62	0.005 HNO ₃ (55)
E	Zn ²⁺	2.65	2.62	2.64	1.97	1.98	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ (70)
	Cu ²⁺	2.85	2.45	2.65	2.74	2.70	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ (50)
	Cd ²⁺	1.85	1.76	1.79	2.20	2.12	0.005 HNO ₃ (55)
F	Zn ²⁺	2.65	2.65	2.64	1.99	1.88	0.050 H ₂ SO ₄ (70)
	Cd ²⁺	1.85	1.66	1.68	3.12	3.16	0.010 HNO ₃ (55)
	Ni ²⁺	2.15	2.08	2.09	1.52	1.33	0.005 H ₂ SO ₄ (50)

[Column : Internal diameter 0.08 cm, bed height 8 cm, flow rate 1 mL/min, pH 5.5, temp. 25 °C]

(CT, AAS and RSD stand for 'Complexometric Titration', 'Atomic Absorption Spectrometry' and 'Relative Standard Derivation' respectively)

the column with the help of 0.05 M H₂SO₄ in the case of mixture A, and then Cd²⁺ was desorbed with 0.01 M HNO₃. Similarly other diverse metal ions were separated from Zn²⁺ using different eluents as shown in Table 4 (B to C). Required volume of each eluents for complete separation is given in the Table 2. After recovery, metal ions were determined complexometrically. The relative standard deviation (RSD) values indicate that the present method is almost similarly reported earlier²⁸.

In order to assess the analytical application, the proposed method was applied to separate Zn²⁺ from multi component synthetic mixture (E to F, Table 4) containing zinc with different metal ions commonly associated with electroplating waste and belong in the same analytical group. A clean separation of Zn²⁺ from ternary synthetic mixture (E) is exhibited by a representative elution curve (Fig. 6). Results show high degree of effectiveness and utility of the prepared method (elution curves are not overlapped). Here it is worth mentioning that both CT

Fig. 6. Elution profile of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Ni²⁺ mixture.

(complexometry titration) and AAS (atomic absorption spectrometry) techniques of metal ion measurement provide comparable results.

Conclusion :

The synthesized hydrogels acts as cation exchanger with high exchange capacity. It has good chemical and thermal stability. Exchange bed could be used more than 32 cycles with little loss of exchange capacity. The developed technique could be applied for the selective extraction of Zn^{II} from environmental samples. The proposed method is highly efficient, cost effective, simple and rapid.

The cross-linked MA-g-PVA has significantly higher zinc ion uptake capacity and selectivity than that of uncross-linked MA-g-PVA and commercially available carboxylic resins. The retention and elution of zinc ion took place mainly by ion-exchange process. The synthesized exchanger has strong affinity with zinc ion over nickel and cadmium ions.

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